

Studies on Mixed Ligand Complexes of Adenine and Xanthine with some Rare Earth Ions

P R RASTOGI, MAMTA SINGH and RAM NAYAN*

Department of Chemistry, Hindu College, Moradabad-244 001

Manuscript received 21 April 1992, revised 29 January 1993, accepted 18 March 1993

Interactions of 6-aminopurine (adenine, HA) and 2,6-dihydroxypurine (xanthine, HB) with trivalent rare earth ions Y, Tb, Dy, Ho, Er and Tm, have been studied by pH-titration methods in aqueous solution at 20° ($\mu = 0.1 M KNO_3$). The ligands in their mixtures with tripositive rare earth ions (M^{3+}) form a number of mixed ligand complexes, M^{3+} -adenine-xanthine, M^{3+} -(adenine)₂-xanthine, M^{3+} -adenine-(xanthine)₂ in addition to the binary complexes, M^{3+} -(adenine), M^{3+} -(adenine)₂, M^{3+} -(adenine)₃, M^{3+} -(xanthine), M^{3+} -(xanthine)₂, and M^{3+} -(xanthine)₃. The stability constants of these complexes have been evaluated and the results discussed.

There is growing interest in the studies on metal complexes of biologically important ligands¹ which are likely to be important as models for metalloenzymes-substrate complexes, as components of multi-metal-multi-ligand systems in biological fluids and also in many other biological systems. Purine derivatives are of particular interest due to their being essential constituents of RNA and DNA. Further, clinical efficiency of several purine derivatives for their use in human cancer therapy has been widely appreciated². Also, the metal complexes of purines, pyrimidines and their nucleotides play dominant role in many biochemical systems, and thus their formation have largely been studied involving bipo-sitive metal ions³⁻⁵. Interaction of only few tripositive cations, e.g. Cr, Co and Eu have been reported⁶. Study on complex formation by tripositive rare earth ions with biologically important ligands is in progress due to their role in biochemical processes⁷.

Thus, here the binary and ternary complex formation reactions of some trivalent rare earth ions (Y, Tb, Dy, Ho, Er and Tm³⁺) involving adenine (HA) and xanthine (HB) have been studied in aqueous solution and the complexing behaviour of the two ligands towards the tripositive rare earth ions in the formation of mixed ligand species has been discussed.

Results and Discussion

Proton-ligand dissociation constant : A sharp inflection in pH vs α curve of adenine at $\alpha=0$ with minimum and maximum values -1 and $+1$ respectively (Fig. 1; curve omitted at low pH range),

Fig. 1 pH vs α curves of Dy³⁺-adenine (HA)-xanthine (HB) complex systems (1) HA, (2) HB, (3) Dy³⁺-HA, (4) Dy³⁺-2HA, (5) Dy³⁺-3HA, (6) Dy³⁺-HB, (7) Dy³⁺-2HB, (8) Dy³⁺-3HB, (9) Dy³⁺-HA-HB, (10) Dy³⁺-2HA-HB, (11) Dy³⁺-HA-2HB

indicates stepwise dissociation of protons from protonated amine and imino groups. The logarithm of proton-ligand stability constants evaluated by the previously described method⁸ are : $\log K_1^H = 9.95$ and $\log K_2^H = 4.25$. Further, from a comparison of values obtained in the present work with those of adenine [$(\log K_1^H = 9.88, \log K_2^H = 4.25, 25^\circ, \mu = 0.05 M NaClO_4)^9, (\log K_1^H = 9.83, \log K_2^H = 4.25, 25^\circ, \mu = 0.1 M KNO_3)^{10}, (\log K_1^H = 9.16, \log K_2^H = 4.19, 30^\circ, \mu = 0.1 M KNO_3)^5, (\log K_1^H = 9.19, \log K_2^H = 3.89, 45^\circ, \mu = 0.1 M KNO_3)^4$] and purine ($\log K_1^H = 8.75, 25^\circ, \mu = 0.05 M NaClO_4$)⁹ reported by earlier workers, it is concluded that K_1^H and K_2^H values are for imino and amine groups, respectively.

Basic or electron-donating property of NH_2 group in adenine is responsible for lower value of the proton-ligand dissociation constant of imino group (in adenine) than that of purine.

pH vs a curves of xanthine indicate that a values lie between 0 and 1. Thus, only one proton,

from imino group, is liberated under the experimental condition of pH. The value of the corresponding proton-ligand dissociation constant calculated as usual is $10^{-7.61}$

Binary complexes : Formation of MA^{2+} species at low pH values is evident from pH vs a curve of 1 : 1, metal-adenine mixture. The mixtures containing trivalent Y, Tb, Dy, Ho, Er and Tm become turbid above pH ~ 7.6, 8.0, 7.7, 7.6, 7.6 and 7.5 respectively, and thus beyond these pH values calculations could not be made. Equilibrium constants (K_1) for the reaction, $M^{3+} + A^- \rightleftharpoons MA^{2+}$, evaluated by the previously described methods, are given in Table 1. Their order, $Y^{3+} < Tb^{3+} < Dy^{3+} < Ho^{3+} < Er^{3+} < Tm^{3+}$, shows that complexing tendency of the metal ions increases with decreasing ionic size.

1 : 2, metal-ligand mixtures turn turbid from pH ~ 8.1, 8.1, 7.8, 8.3, 8.3 and 8.3 respectively, in trivalent Y, Tb, Dy, Ho, Er and Tm systems. Simultaneous existence of both the 1:1 and 1:2, metal-adenine species in solution below these pH values, is evident from the titration curves showing no inflections. The equilibrium constant, K_2 of MA_2^+

TABLE I—EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANTS OF BINARY AND MIXED LIGAND COMPLEXES OF ADENINE AND XANTHINE

Temp = 20, $\mu = 0.1 M (KNO_3)$

Reaction	log K					
	Y^{3+}	Tb^{3+}	Dy^{3+}	Ho^{3+}	Er^{3+}	Tm^{3+}
$M^{3+} + A^- \rightleftharpoons MA^{2+}$	5.66±.15	5.73±29	5.86±26	6.12±35	6.13±46	6.15±37
$MA^{2+} + A^- \rightleftharpoons MA_2^+$	5.55±13	5.54±18	5.79±04	5.92±15	5.93±21	5.96±25
$MA_2^+ + A^- \rightleftharpoons MA_3$	5.33±08	5.24±28	5.58±19	5.59±20	5.63±23	5.71±20
$M^{3+} + 3A^- \rightleftharpoons MA_3$	16.54	16.61	17.23	17.63	17.69	17.84
$M^{3+} + B^- \rightleftharpoons MB^{2+}$	4.21±09	4.13±06	4.21±05	4.22±05	4.29±13	4.33±13
$MB^{2+} + B^- \rightleftharpoons MB_2^+$	3.52±12	3.45±05	3.48±06	3.49±09	3.56±09	3.58±10
$MB_2^+ + B^- \rightleftharpoons MB_3$	3.43±05	3.27±04	3.30±15	3.42±09	3.39±14	3.44±13
$M^{3+} + 3B^- \rightleftharpoons MB_3$	11.16	10.94	10.99	11.13	11.24	11.35
$M^{3+} + A^- + B^- \rightleftharpoons MAB^+$	11.62±09	11.44±14	11.59±06	11.67±06	11.83±07	11.98±06
$MA^{2+} + B^- \rightleftharpoons MAB^+$	5.96	5.71	5.73	5.55	5.70	5.83
$MB^{2+} + A^- \rightleftharpoons MAB^+$	7.41	7.37	7.38	7.45	7.54	7.63
$M^{3+} + 2B^- + A^- \rightleftharpoons MB_2A$	16.92±37	16.59±24	17.07±37	17.09±24	17.27±45	17.85±35
$MB_2^+ + A^- \rightleftharpoons MB_2A$	9.19	9.00	9.38	9.38	9.42	9.94
$MA^{2+} + 2B^- \rightleftharpoons MB_2A$	11.26	10.85	11.27	10.97	11.14	11.70
$M^{3+} + 2A^- + B^- \rightleftharpoons MA_2B$	18.90±41	18.49±50	18.88±43	19.03±34	19.09±30	19.59±35
$MA_2^+ + B^- \rightleftharpoons MA_2B$	7.69	7.22	7.23	6.99	6.96	7.46
$MB^{2+} + 2A^- \rightleftharpoons MBA_2$	14.69	14.36	14.67	14.81	14.73	15.26

complex species are reported in Table 1. K_2 values are smaller than the corresponding K_1 values, but their differences are not very significant due to formation of MA^{2+} and MA_2^+ species in a single step. Stability constant for the reaction between MA^{2+} and A^- follows the order : $YA^{2+} \approx TbA^{2+} < DyA^{2+} < HoA^{2+} < ErA^{2+} < TmA^{2+}$.

Appearance of turbidity has been noted in 1 : 3, metal-adenine mixtures at higher pH values (i.e. at \sim pH 8.6, 8.3, 8.5, 9.2, 8.7 and 8.6 respectively, for the trivalent Y, Tb, Dy, Ho, Er and Tm systems). The titration curves indicate that MA^{2+} , MA_2^+ and MA_3 species are formed in a single step, where equilibrium constant K_3 is smaller than K_2 or K_1 but the difference of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ is greater than that of $\log K_2$ and $\log K_3$, in each metal system.

The 1 : 1, metal-xanthine mixtures of trivalent Y, Tb, Dy, Ho, Er and Tm turn turbid at pH \sim 7.7 in Y and at pH \sim 7.5 in rest of the systems. K_1 values (very close to each other) almost follow the increasing trend with the decrease in the basicity of the rare earth ions. The 1 : 2, metal (Y, Tb, Dy, Ho, Er and Tm)-ligand mixtures also turn turbid from pH \sim 7.9, 7.8, 7.6, 7.6, 7.7 and 7.6 respectively. The evaluated K_2 values in solution are also very close to each other and follow almost a regular trend of increase in its values with decrease of size of the metal ion. Stability constants K_3 calculated below the pH of precipitation (i.e. below pH \sim 7.8, 8.0, 7.9, 7.9, 7.9 and 7.9 respectively, in trivalent Y, Tb, Dy, Ho, Er and Tm complex systems) are given in Table 1. Like the 1 : 1 or 1 : 2, metal-ligand complexes, there is no appreciable variation in K_3 value in the studied metal-xanthine complexes.

A comparison of overall stability constants indicates that chelating tendency of adenine is greater than that of xanthine. Poor rare earth-xanthine association may be because of lower electron-donating nature of the C=O group, while a phenolic oxygen possesses stronger donor properties than other atoms¹¹.

Mixed ligand complexes : Turbidity appears from pH \sim 7.8 in Y^{3+} and from pH \sim 7.6 in rest of the systems in 1 : 1 : 1 mixtures of the trivalent metals (Y, Tb, Dy, Ho, Er and Tm) with adenine-xanthine. However, the titration curves (Fig. 1, for Dy^{3+} system, others omitted) indicate the formation of the ternary complex species in solution below the pH of precipitation. Substituting the proton-ligand dissociation constants of ligands and the equilibrium constants of their binary complexes into mass and charge balance relations, concentrations of free ligands were calculated by Newton-Raphson method as described earlier⁸. Further, concentration of other species were obtained and the equilibrium constants of the mixed ligand species MAB were evaluated (Table 1). The data indicate that mixed ligand complex formation is highly favourable in all the systems.

From a comparison of equilibrium constants it is indicated that addition of a ligand to the 1 : 1 rare earth complex with other ligand is higher than for the addition of the same ligand to the aqua-ion. The values are higher by 1.75 to 1.33 logarithm units. Similar trend has been noted earlier¹² for the reaction $Cu(bipy) + L \rightleftharpoons Cu(bipy)L$ (where, bipy is 2,2'-bipyridyl and L is the anion of salicylic acid, catechol or tiron).

Formation of the 1 : 1 : 2, metal-adenine-xanthine, metal-xanthine-adenine complexes is also evident from the corresponding titration curves. However, analysis of the data could not be made at higher pH values due to the appearance of turbidity from pH \sim 7.6, in the systems where xanthine is excess and from pH \sim 7.9, 7.8, 7.8, 7.8, 7.8, and 7.7, respectively in 1 : 1 : 2 mixtures of tripositive rare earth ions (Y, Tb, Dy, Ho, Er and Tm) with xanthine-adenine.

The higher values of equilibrium constants of the mixed ligand complexes are probably favoured by electrostatic interaction between amino-hydrogen of the adenine and the oxygen (C=O) of xanthine. These findings are in agreement with the earlier results¹³ obtained in the formation of $Ni(\text{serine})_2$ -(ethylenediamine) and $Ni(\text{serine})_2$ -(histamine).

Experimental

Standard solutions of 0.1273 *N* NaOH, 1.0 *M* KNO₃ and 0.0234 *N* HNO₃ were prepared using analytical grade reagents. Y³⁺, Tb³⁺, Dy³⁺, Ho³⁺, Er³⁺ and Tm³⁺ carbonates were precipitated from their chloride salts (Johnson Matthey). Excess of the rare earth metal carbonate was treated with standard nitric acid solution and filtered. Metal content was determined in the filtrate gravimetrically after precipitation as oxalate and subsequent ignition to oxide. Aqueous solutions of each 6-aminopurine (adenine, HA) and 2,6-dihydropurine (xanthine, HB) (each, Loba Chemie) were prepared by direct weighing.

Following aqueous mixtures were prepared : (i) 0.00234 *N* HNO₃; (ii) 5.0×10^{-4} *M* ligand + (i); (iii) 5.0×10^{-4} *M* metal nitrate + (ii); (iv) 2.5×10^{-4} *M* metal nitrate + (ii); (v) 1.66×10^{-4} *M* metal nitrate + (ii); (vi) metal nitrate + adenine + xanthine + (i) ($C_{MO} = C_{AO} = C_{BO} = 5.0 \times 10^{-4}$ *M*, where C_{MO} , C_{AO} , and C_{BO} are total initial metal, adenine and xanthine concentrations, respectively); (vii) metal nitrate + adenine + xanthine + (i) ($C_{MO} = 1/2 C_{AO} = C_{BO} = 5.0 \times 10^{-4}$ *M*), (viii) metal nitrate + adenine + xanthine + (i) ($C_{MO} = C_{AO} = 1/2 C_{BO} = 5.0 \times 10^{-4}$ *M*) and were titrated as described earlier against sodium hydroxide solution (0.1273 *N*) using a Systronic 335 pH-meter.

Experiments were carried out, keeping the initial volume of each mixture 50 cm³ at an ionic strength of 0.1 *M* (KNO₃) and 20° temperature. The alkali solution was added from a micro-burette and the corresponding pH-meter readings were noted. The titrations were continued to a pH of ~ 11.0.

From the experimental data, pH vs volume of alkali curves were plotted and were utilised to calculate moles of alkali used per mole of ligand (*a*) at various pH. The *a* values were further plotted against pH, and the titration curves thus obtained were analysed as described earlier, for obtaining information on metal-ligand interactions.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Professor Arun K. Dey, University of Allahabad, for valuable discussion and suggestions.

References

1. J. ARPOLAHTI and E. OTTOILA, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1985, **107**, 105; H. BAUER, G. M. SHELDRIK and U. B. W. NAGEL, *Z. Naturforsch., Teil B*, 1985, **40**, 1237; C. M. S. MIKULSKI, N. DEFENDCO and K. N. M. DUAL, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1982, **67**, 61; R. PRADES, L. G. STADTHER, H. DONATE and R. B. MARTIN, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1974, **36**, 689; R. C. STEWART, R. HILLE and V. NASSEY, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1984, **259**, 14426.
2. G. B. BROWN, *Texas Rep. Biol. Med.*, 1952, **10**, 961.
3. R. L. KARPEL, K. KUSTIN and M. A. WOLFF, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1971, **75**, 799; K. H. SCHELLER, F. HOFSTELTER, R. PAUL, MITCHEL, B. PRIJS and H. SIGEL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **103**, 447; M. M. TAQUI KHAN and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **88**, 668.
4. M. M. TAQUI KHAN and C. R. KRISHNAMOORTHY, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1971, **33**, 1417.
5. R. NAYAN and A. K. DEY, *Z. Naturforsch., Teil B*, 1972, **27**, 688.
6. J. GALEA, R. BACCARIA, G. FERRONI and J. P. BELOICH, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1978, **23**, 647; C. R. KRISHNAMOORTHY, R. VAN ELDIK and G. M. HARRIS, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1980, **10**, 195.
7. D. W. DARNALL and E. R. BIRNBAUM, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1970, **245**, 6484; *Biochemistry*, 1973, **12**, 3489; *Met. Ions Biol. Systems*, 1976, **6**, 275; H. SIGEL, *Met. Ions Biol. Systems*, 1973, **2**, 65; 1976, **5**, 148, 250; 1979, **9**, 66, 1320; SABHAPATI, Ph.D. Thesis, Rohilkhand University, 1987.
8. R. NAYAN and A. K. DEY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1976, **14**, 892; R. NAYAN, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1981, **43**, 383.
9. N. REINERT and R. WEISS, *Hoppe Seyler's Z. Physiol. Chem.*, 1969, **350**, 1310.
10. A. ALBERT and E. P. SERJENT, *Biochem J.*, 1960, **76**, 621.
11. E. R. BIRNBAUM and T. MOELLER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **91**, 7274; L. T. CHARPENTIER and T. MOELLER, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1970, **32**, 3575; J. H. FORSBERG and T. MOELLER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1969, **8**, 883, 889; R. C. GRAHDEY and T. MOELLER, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1970, **32**, 333.
12. G. A. L'ETEVREUX and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1966, **28**, 481.
13. D. D. PERRIN and V. S. SHARMA, *J. Chem. Sec. (A)*, 1968, 446.